

Towards developing a suitable Open Access policy for India

India is one of the largest academic publishing countries in the world. A country-wise analysis of publications and publication models in Web of Science from 2006 to 2015 revealed that, India ranked 3rd in publishing in open access journal and 10th in overall research output. The number of Indian publications in OA journals was 2% higher than the global average¹.

Open access definition

OPEN access (OA) refers to an academic movement where publications are made available and accessible free of cost with minimum restrictions to different kinds of audience. The Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI), first defined 'Open Access' as 'making the publications freely available on public internet, permitting any user to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial legal or technical barriers'². It is a means to build a society where information is available at free of cost, round the clock, and for all the age groups, and at all the places. The OA policies and mandates makes necessary that the scholars and researchers must publish their works in open access, as they have received research funding from public money. These documents also proposed that scholarly publications should be free and easily available to read and reproduce for all concerned, with proper citation to the original source.

OA gives major benefits to authors, readers, funders, institutions, etc. and more so for developing and under-developed countries, where enough resources are not readily available to academicians where they have to pay the access charges. OA may save financial resources spent on library subscriptions for content of traditionally-published journals.

There are various forms of OA. There are journals in which articles published are entirely OA where all the articles are openly accessible to everyone. Then, there are journals which make their published articles accessible or made free after payment of article processing fee or on their own after a particular period from the date of publication. Based on the levels and types of OA, the articles can be classified into the following categories-

Gold open access: This refers to an article which is published in a journal that is OA, i.e. it is in a journal where all articles are accessible to everyone without any cost/charges.

Green open access: This refers to an article published in a journal which can be accessed through payment but the article is uploaded on some repository (either disciplinary or institutional), which makes it accessible free of cost. However, in this case the reuse rights are restricted. Here, journals impose an embargo period (varying from 6 to 48 months), after which the article can be uploaded on such a repository.

Hybrid open access: This refers to an article published in a journal which is not open to many and makes it publicly accessible or OA if article processing charges is borne by author or the interested institution through some agreement with the journal.

India's initiatives for open access

Sixteen institutes in India are having OA mandates for publishing their works in their institutional repositories. However, it is also observed that 79 institutions are preserving some kind of documents in their Institutional Repositories. The Indian scientific community has made notable efforts toward OA not only through journals, but also through institutional repositories at major scientific hubs such as the Indian Institute of Science. Also, OA repositories for theses, such as the Shodhganga initiative, are admirable government-funded efforts to promote the worldwide accessibility of Indian research³. In global context, the percentage of OA publications from India is significant, and Indian journals are more available on OA repositories such as Pubmed Central, and Directory of Open Access Journals.

In DOAJ(Directory of Open Access Journals, Germany),there are 236 active open access journals published from India and have been listed as of May 2018. According to OpenDOAR (Directory of Open Access Repositories,UK), India has 79 open access repositories comprising of research institutions and academic institutions, while some of them are both research and academic institutions. Following are some of the academic institutions from India that have been maintaining OA repositories of variant kinds of documents: Aligarh Muslim University, Bangalore University, Cochin University of Science & Technology (CUSAT), Goa University, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay (IITB), IIT Kanpur (Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur), Indian Institute of Management Kozhikode (IIMK), Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad, Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bengaluru, Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee, Indian Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), Information and Library Network Center (INFLIBNET), Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, National Institute of Technology, Rourkela (NITR), Osmania University, Hyderabad⁴.

In 2009, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi⁵ sent a Memorandum to its 37 laboratories to set up institutional OA repositories. The Government of India (GoI) initiatives' towards OA is Open Access Policy, released in 2014 which is jointly issued by DBT and DST, the two departments of the Ministry of Science and Technology, and states that 'since all funds disbursed by the DBT and DST are public funds, it is important that the information and knowledge generated through the use of these funds are made publicly available as soon as possible...'. The guiding principle is public access to publicly funded research outcome. Through the Policy, institutions were encouraged to set up repositories and deposit all their research outcomes in them. A central harvester sciencecentral.in was also established and it was expected that all institutional repositories will be eventually linked to it. The Policy was mandatorily to be followed by institutions receiving core funding from DBT and DST. The csircentral.net established by CSIRURDIP⁶ is another example of central harvester that is expected to link the different institutional repositories of individual CSIR laboratories. Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) has also set up a central repository called 'krishikosh'. The more recent National Digital Library⁷ project of the Ministry of Human Resources and Development, GoI tried to bring the repository culture to higher education institutions in the country. However, full benefits of these initiatives are yet to be realized.

Challenges

One of the major challenge of OA is low-quality or predatory OA journals, and the lack of funds to afford OA publication charges. In 2015, a Web of Science-based analysis of more than 1000 papers from a conglomerate of IITs revealed that 69% of these were for OA, including 58% for green OA. Alarmingly, the papers posted on institutional repositories and on websites such as ResearchGate were not compliant with the green OA standards⁸. The Bohannon sting study revealed and exposed substandard or no quality checks in journals claiming to be peer-reviewed and more than 80% of the journals based in India accepted the dummy manuscript⁹. The identification of such poor quality OA journals was also highlighted by the work of Jeffrey Beall, a North American librarian who coined the term “predatory publishing”¹⁰. An analysis of responses from 480 corresponding authors from India who published in substandard journals pointed to the fact that more than half of these authors were not aware that the journals were ‘predatory’. A majority of such authors bore the publication charges themselves¹¹. There were 318 OA journals published from India in 2016 which were indexed in DOAJ. As of July 2015, DOAJ indexed 576 Indian OA journals, as stated by GOAP (Global open Access Portal) of UNESCO. Compared to the preceding years (2015; 2016; and 2017), now in the year 2018, there are only 236 journals listed in DOAJ. Many of them have now been deleted from DOAJ as they could not stand for the test of quality and ethical publishing norms¹².

A survey of more than 500 researchers from India revealed that the major reason for the underutilization of institutional repositories were concerns regarding plagiarism and copyright of articles submitted to such repositories¹³. This suggests that there is still a need to sensitize stakeholders about unethical scientific practices. A major impediment toward publishing in OA journals was a perceived as lack of prestige of such journals which charged fees from authors¹⁴.

Indian scholars and researchers have to struggle for access to research services which may be considered routine in other parts of the globe, such as plagiarism checks and access to Scopus, Web of Science, and subscription-based aggregators of information. Therefore, it is highly unlikely that Indian researchers or their institutions will be able to afford OA publication fees in the majority of instances.

Measures

To minimize the OA challenges, there is a need to increase awareness amongst Indian academicians regarding publication practices, including OA, and its potential benefits, while avoiding falling prey to poor quality OA journals. Opening institutional repositories should be encouraged in all major institutions which are run by state and central government, and their uptake should be promoted to the faculty. There is a need to incorporate the principles of scientific writing and ethical publishing in students right from an early age. The courses in these subjects may be made compulsory for all under- and postgraduate students and efforts should be made to teach students and faculty regarding publishing and ethics of publishing. These would make them aware about predatory journals and clear all the doubts about OA publishing. There should be revision of promotion criteria to incorporate an actual quality assessment of the published work by the assessor, rather than relying on bibliometric indicators, such as the impact factor, will also can improve the overall standards of publishing.

It is now required that all the Indian Councils, like CSIR, ICAR, MCI, etc, and AICTE, UGC have to come out with OA mandates / policies for the country, so that all the academics, researchers of research centers and universities, including technical universities, publish their research output in Open Access.

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